

The Numbers of Fear: Methodological Note and Results

Agnese Vardanega

Claudia Vardanega

October 1, 2025

Abstract

This report presents the methodology and results of a quantitative content analysis of Italian media discourse during the first COVID-19 lockdown (February-May 2020). The study investigates the hypothesis that the pandemic narrative was ‘dataist’—marked by a separation between numerical reporting and scientific context—and carried an anxiety-inducing emotional profile consistent with post-truth dynamics.

Based on a corpus of 2,144 news headlines, we employed LDA to identify themes and sentiment analysis to assess their emotional tone. Our findings reveal a clear thematic divide between a “numbers” cluster (themes *Numeri*, *Bollettini*) and a “disciplinary” cluster (*Scienza*, *Esperti*, *Misure*). The “numbers” cluster, in particular, is associated with a negative, high-arousal emotional profile. These results support the initial hypothesis that the “datafication” of the pandemic narrative (data without context) functioned as a driver of emotional activation.

This document accompanies the presentation “I numeri della paura: governamentalità pandemica fra opacità e trasparenza” (“The Numbers of Fear: Pandemic Governmentality between Opacity and Transparency”), presented at the conference “The Great Fear: Epidemics in the Italian Peninsula from the 17th Century to Today,” University of Teramo, September 30 - October 1, 2025. Its purpose is to make the data discussed on that occasion available.

1 Introduction

The results of a content analysis performed on the headlines of news related to the coronavirus during the first lockdown period are presented.

The first part of this study aimed to *explore the discourse surrounding the pandemic*, as it was constituted in the first phase of the coronavirus spread (February 22 - May 15, 2020; §2), through the identification of themes, actors, and categories.

The hypothesis at the center of this report is that the pandemic data were presented in a “dataist” manner (Van Dijck, 2014), and that this conception of data is closely linked with post-truth (Shelton, 2020), understood as a set of discursive practices and shared beliefs (Ferraris, 2017; Lorusso, 2018).

The Latent Dirichlet Allocation (§3) and sentiment analysis presented in this document provided data to support the first hypothesis. The narrative of the data (theme *Numeri*: Numbers) was:

- clearly separated from that of *Scienza* (Science), *Esperti* (Experts), and *Misure* (government Measures) (§3.1);
- prevalent, and grew over time, at the expense of other themes (§3.2), in a process of *datafication* of the narrative;
- characterized by an anxiety-inducing emotional profile, while institutional communication (*Scienza*, *Esperti*, and *Misure*) followed the standards of emergency communication (positive, calm, in control; §4). The data became a tool for emotional activation rather than information.

The last part of the presentation concerned the qualitative analysis of the counter-narratives presented in the articles (and not just in the headlines), and the use of data to support them.

2 The corpus: headlines on Google

We considered the headlines of newspapers and news sites that included the word “coronavirus,” selecting them from the top thirty Google search results, in the period between February 22 and May 15, 2020. This period was chosen in consideration of the volume of user searches for the keyword “coronavirus” on Google (Fig. 1; source: Google Trends). To reduce geolocation (and indexing) bias, we chose a number of results that tended to produce duplicates over the days, ensuring a good variety of local sources.

The collected headlines were pre-processed and analyzed with the help of the R software (R Core Team, 2025)¹.

The choice to focus on the headlines of all search results, rather than on major newspapers, is motivated by two considerations.

- The public often limits themselves to reading headlines, especially on social media.
- Moreover, while in the first weeks of the pandemic (March 2020) the Audiweb rankings were led by Repubblica and Corriere della Sera, followed by TgCom24 and Il Messaggero (Cazzola, 2020a), those on social interactions show the relevance of free news outlets like Fanpage.it (third, preceded by Corriere and followed in fifth place by Repubblica: Cazzola, 2020c). The Comscore ranking for the same period is led by the publisher of Fanpage (Ciaopeople), while Il Corriere della Sera is only in sixth position (Cazzola, 2020b).

While the sample cannot be said to be representative of what was published by news sites, it is indicative of the type of news that had the greatest circulation in the considered period: a total of 2,144 headlines², for 248 online outlets (national, local, television; Table 1).

Figure 1: Web searches for the terms ”coronavirus” and ”covid”

Dates represented in the graph. February 23: Establishment of the first red zone (peak of searches); March 9: The “escape from the North”; March 11: “Cura Italia” decree (“I stay at home”); April 4: mandatory masks; April 18: postponement of the easing of restrictive measures; May 16: Phase 2 Decree.

¹In particular, the *Quanteda* (Benoit et al., 2025) and *topicmodels* (Grün & Hornik, 2024; see also Phan et al., 2008)

Table 1: Main news outlets included in the sample

News outlet	N	News outlet	N
corriere.it	130	picchionews.it	9
repubblica.it	117	vanityfair.it	9
lastampa.it	101	vita.it	9
ilsole24ore.com	88	ecodibergamo.it	8
ilmessaggero.it	87	corrierecomunicazioni.it	7
ansa.it	86	forbes.it	7
ilfattoquotidiano.it	82	ilcentro.it	7
tgcom24.mediaset.it	69	luccaindiretta.it	7
rainews.it	63	varesenews.it	7
open.online	53	corrieredicomo.it	6
adnkronos.com	52	infodata.ilsole24ore.com	6
lanazione.it	41	ispionline.it	6
tg24.sky.it	41	money.it	6
ilrestodelcarlino.it	39	nationalgeographic.it	6
agi.it	37	affaritaliani.it	5
quotidiano.net	37	askanews.it	5
ilpost.it	35	avvenire.it	5
genova24.it	33	chietitoday.it	5
ilgiorno.it	33	corriereadriatico.it	5
wired.it	33	corriereromagna.it	5
ivg.it	30	cremonaoggi.it	5
ilcittadinomb.it	29	fondazioneveronesi.it	5
lanuovasardegna.it	22	gazzetta.it	5
ilmattino.it	18	ildolomiti.it	5
internazionale.it	17	ilgazzettino.it	5
lagazzettadelmezzogiorno.it	17	ilmeteo.it	5
liberoquotidiano.it	17	ilpescara.it	5
laprovinciacr.it	16	it.businessinsider.com	5
lavocedeltrentino.it	16	lasiciliaweb.it	5
altalex.com	15	milanotoday.it	5
formiche.net	15	motori.virgilio.it	5
iltempo.it	15	nonsprecare.it	5
ilgiunco.net	14	rete8.it	5
quifinanza.it	14	romatoday.it	5
sport.sky.it	14	vaticannews.va	5
fanpage.it	13	bolognatoday.it	4
iltirreno.gelocal.it	13	corrieredellumbria.corr.it	4
corrieredellosport.it	12	ilpiccolo.net	4
lapressa.it	12	iodonna.it	4
focus.it	11	osservatoriomalattierare.it	4
la7.it	11	ravennanotizie.it	4
bergamonews.it	10	sulpanaro.net	4
ilcapoluogo.it	10		
ilfoglio.it	10		
ilsecoloxix.it	10		
riviera24.it	10		
salute.gov.it	10		
ilfattoalimentare.it	9		
m.cronachemaceratesi.it	9		
medicalfacts.it	9		

3 Topic modeling: LDA

The topic modeling analysis was conducted on a matrix defined by 625 “characterizing” terms, i.e., with high relative frequency but present in a limited number of texts (10%). Following the term reduction, the number of analyzable headlines became 2,102.

To determine the number of topics to extract and the distribution’s α parameter (which regulates the number of topics attributed to each document), we tested several models³. Finally, a 7-topic model with α equal to 0.2 was chosen⁴.

Figure 2: LDA. Composition of the themes: “numbers” cluster

In LDA (D. Blei et al., 2001; D. M. Blei et al., 2003), a topic is defined as a latent dimension that organizes the vocabulary of a corpus. The procedure reconstructs a posterior distribution of terms for each topic (β matrix), and one of topics for each headline (γ matrix)⁵. This is a technique we could call *inductive*, thus suitable for the type of sample used, for exploratory purposes.

Semantic interpretation of the themes This is achieved by using the information in the β matrix (terms-topics). Figs. 2 and 3 present the 10 most significant terms for each theme (the measure is not indicative of frequency).

For the purpose of the comparison relevant here, five of the seven themes are divided into two main macro-clusters (§3.1):

packages.

²2,555 after removing duplicates, which become 2,144 after eliminating those outside the date range or not classifiable as “news.”

³With the *ldatuning* package (for calculating the optimal number of clusters: Nikita, 2020) and *topicdoc* (for a posteriori quality measures: Friedman, 2022).

⁴To reduce the topics assignable to each document, compared to the default parameter (0.1), given the brevity of the texts.

⁵For the application of this technique to very short texts, cf. Albalawi et al. (2020).

- a **disciplinary** cluster (cool colors): *Scienza* (Science), *Esperti* (Experts), and *Misure* (Measures) and
- a **numbers** cluster (warm colors): *Numeri* (Numbers) and *Bollettini* (Bulletins).⁶

The *Cronaca* (Daily News) theme largely follows the behavior of the latter, while the *Esteri* (World) theme is quite varied in its composition.

Figure 3: LDA. Composition of the themes: "disciplinary" cluster

Evaluation of the results For the evaluation of the themes, a series of information was considered, also relevant for our discourse, and in particular to show that:

- the most widespread themes are *Numeri* and *Scienza*;
- the *Numeri* and *Bollettini* themes are not very varied and not very informative, in the sense that they contain rather common terms (which do not stand out from the corpus);
- while, on the contrary, the *Scienza* theme is the most informative and semantically varied.

The measures, presented in Table 2, can be read as follows⁷:

- **Prominence**: number of documents in which a theme is present (regardless of its weight).
- **Frequency**: number of documents uniquely assigned to the theme (based on the highest value).
- **Size**: the number of terms or fractions of terms present in the distribution of each theme. The total is 625, the number of terms in the matrix.

⁶Theme glossary: *Scienza* = Science; *Esperti* = Experts; *Misure* = (government) Measures; *Numeri* = Numbers; *Bollettini* = (Civil Protection) Bulletins; *Cronaca* = Daily News; *Esteri* = World News.

⁷Other available measures, such as the distance in terms of tf-idf and the coherence index, which refer to the distributions of terms in the texts, are not appropriate in this case, given the brevity of the texts themselves (for details on the calculation and use of the measures, cf. [Airoldi et al., 2015, p. 238 et seq.](#)).

Table 2: Theme characteristics

Theme	Prominence (no. headlines)	Frequency	Size (terms)	Exclusivity (terms)	Distance from corpus
Misure	436	214	109,52	9,68	0,60
Esteri	422	201	94,44	9,64	0,58
Cronaca	461	212	89,32	9,69	0,57
Esperti	446	204	104,40	9,47	0,60
Scienza	465	268	113,13	9,58	0,61
Numeri	539	306	67,27	9,66	0,55
Bollettini	416	226	46,91	9,86	0,59
Total	2.102	1.631	625,00	10,00	–

- The most semantically varied theme is *Scienza*;
- The least differentiated is *Bollettini*, preceded by *Numeri* (after all, numbers are not included in the term-document matrix).
- **Exclusivity**: how many of the most important terms (the top ten, for example) are *exclusive* to the theme itself. Considering the technique adopted, the brevity of the texts, and the chosen α value, we have a strong specificity of the themes (see also Fig. 5). This means that the themes are well-distinct from each other.
- **Distance** (Hellinger) from the corpus: divergence between the distribution of terms in the theme and that in the entire corpus. The greater the distance, the more informative the identified theme is:
 - the most distant/informative is *Scienza*.
 - the least distant is *Numeri*.

Figure 4: LDA. Dendrogram of the themes

3.1 The separation of “numbers” and science

While the two most frequent and transversal themes, *Numeri* and *Scienza* represent completely distinct “narratives” of the pandemic.

The dendrogram in Fig. 4 highlights that the numbers macro-cluster (*Numeri* and *Bollettini*) separates clearly and immediately from the other themes, particularly from *Scienza* and *Esperti*.

This also emerges in more detail in the graph in Fig. 5, which represents the connections between themes and terms (i.e., the β matrix). The presence of connections (shared terms) between themes can be interpreted as indicative of semantic proximity.

Figure 5: LDA. Theme-Term Graph (beta)

The table in Fig. 6 provides further confirmation of this separation.

The values represented are the means of the scores from the γ (*gamma*) matrix, which is the probability that a headline is associated with a theme (the threshold is 0.14, i.e., 1 / 7 themes): the strong presence of numbers (3 or more occurrences within the headline) characterizes the *Numeri* and *Bollettini* clusters, while *Scienza* and *Esperti* are characterized by their absence⁸.

N numeri	n	Misure	Esteri	Cronaca	Esperti	Scienza	Numeri	Bollettini
0	1.359	0,16	0,12	0,14	0,17	0,19	0,10	0,12
1	393	0,12	0,15	0,17	0,11	0,10	0,24	0,11
2	272	0,08	0,15	0,10	0,08	0,05	0,29	0,25
3	119	0,05	0,11	0,11	0,05	0,04	0,43	0,20

Figure 6: Mean gamma values of headlines with numbers

⁸The numbers variable represents the count of numbers in the headlines, in words or digits. These *tokens* were identified via POS tagging and then manually corrected, to exclude dates and numbers contained in the expressions such as “covid 19”, “sars-cov 2”, etc. Numbers in digits *did not contribute to the definition of the themes*.

3.2 Numbers prevail over time

The average daily distribution of themes shows how they develop over time (Fig. 7⁹): the *Numeri* theme increasingly accounts for a larger share of the discourse, at the expense, in particular, of *Scienza*, *Esperti*, and *Misure*.

Figure 7: Themes over time (presence; 15-day moving average)

4 Sentiment analysis

The sentiment analysis was carried out with the affective dictionary *ELIta* (Di Palma, 2024b, 2024a), which provides scores for 6,905 Italian lexical forms, on two classifications of emotions: the VAD model (§4.1) and Plutchik’s wheel of emotions (§4.2).

The aggregated scores of the headlines by theme confirm the distance between the two macro-clusters, which have opposite emotional profiles. This result is all the more significant as:

- it relies on two different types of classification of the affective tone of the texts (not simply positive/negative);
- a theme is attributed by the minimum threshold of the γ matrix value, and this tends to flatten the results (each document can belong to multiple themes).

4.1 The VAD model

The VAD model (Russell, 1980; Russell & Mehrabian, 1977), a cornerstone of the dimensional analysis of emotions, is articulated on three dimensions:

⁹Moving average of the daily γ value; the total for each day is one; the significance threshold is 0.14.

Table 3: Mean VAD scores by theme

Theme	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
Bollettini	0,150	0,534	-0,091
Cronaca	0,052	0,549	-0,190
Esperti	0,223	0,448	-0,012
Esteri	0,105	0,534	-0,105
Misure	0,243	0,453	-0,023
Numeri	-0,105	0,560	-0,325
Scienza	0,184	0,504	-0,045
–	0,122	0,512	-0,113

Scale: -4, +4; gamma min.: 0.14

- **Valence.** Affective polarity (unpleasant/pleasant).
- **Arousal.** Physiological and psychological intensity of an emotion. A more arousing emotion is more intense, regardless of its valence.
- **Dominance (control).** The perceived sense of control over a given emotion or situation¹⁰.

The average scores, as mentioned above, are very low — close to zero (neutrality: Table 3). However, the distance between the two macro-clusters is evident when considering the profiles, defined by the differences from the means (Figs. 8 and 9).

Figure 8: VAD: numbers cluster

¹⁰They closely resemble the semantic oppositions identified as primary by Osgood et al. (1956): good-bad (*evaluation*, similar to valence), strong/weak (*activity*, arousal) and active/passive (*power*, dominance).

Table 4: Mean emotion scores by theme

Theme	Joy Serenity	Trust	Fear	Surprise	Sadness	Disgust Rejection	Anger Annoyance	Anticipation Interest
Bollettini	0,325	0,284	0,317	0,308	0,312	0,154	0,212	0,412
Cronaca	0,297	0,293	0,332	0,259	0,305	0,143	0,206	0,396
Esperti	0,320	0,303	0,287	0,262	0,264	0,144	0,203	0,412
Esteri	0,305	0,277	0,341	0,285	0,314	0,165	0,232	0,388
Misure	0,318	0,304	0,297	0,262	0,261	0,139	0,197	0,414
Numeri	0,284	0,263	0,374	0,262	0,351	0,159	0,216	0,348
Scienza	0,312	0,303	0,315	0,262	0,272	0,150	0,211	0,404
–	0,309	0,290	0,323	0,272	0,297	0,151	0,211	0,396

Scale 0-1; gamma min. = 0.14

Figure 9: VAD: disciplinary cluster vs. Numbers

The “dataist” themes (*Numeri*, *Bollettini*, and in some ways *Cronaca*) present a profile characterized by more negative tones, sensationalism (we are talking about headlines), and less control.

The themes of the “disciplinary” macro-cluster (*Scienza*, *Esperti*, *Misure*) show an opposite emotional profile, which aligns with the standards of emergency communication: positive, directive (control), and calm (low arousal).

This opposition is particularly evident between *Numeri* on one side, and *Misure* and *Esperti* on the other.

4.2 The wheel of emotions

The other dimensional classification of emotion provided by *ELIta* is the *Plutchik’s Wheel of Emotions* (Plutchik, 1980), which includes eight basic emotions arranged in opposite pairs: joy - sadness, trust - disgust, fear - anger, anticipation - surprise¹¹.

¹¹The *ELIta* dictionary also includes the emotion “love,” which is a secondary emotion (joy + trust), and which was not used.

Figure 10: Wheel of emotions

Figure 11: Wheel of emotions: numbers cluster

Figure 12: Wheel of emotions: disciplinary cluster vs. Numbers

The graphs in Fig. 10 represents all the themes, already highlighting significant differences. As can be seen, the average scores, while outlining distinct emotional profiles, never reach maximum values: a score of 0.25 means “weak association” with the emotion, or low intensity.

This also depends, as mentioned above (§4), on how the scores are aggregated by theme. On the other hand, a moderate intensity is consistent with the nature of the analyzed texts: it is unlikely that a headline referring to a Civil Protection bulletin, however anxiety-inducing, would arouse ‘terror’ or, however positive, would arouse joy.

This is the reason why, consistent with the graded nature of Plutchik’s model, more nuanced terms have been paired with the stronger ones: serenity (joy) - sadness, trust - rejection (disgust), fear - anger, surprise - interest (anticipation).

The other two graphs (Figs.12 and §11) show the results by dividing the two macro-clusters of interest: this allows for a clearer appreciation of how the “dataist” profile, dominated by fear and sadness (*Numeri*), is contrasted with the “disciplinary” one, characterized by anticipation and trust (Fig. 11).

Table 5: Interventions on the dictionary

Not scored	n	Neutralized	n	Added	n
positivo	239	calo	50	contagio	341
negativo	5	calare	31	decesso	99
positività	3	crescere	20	guarito	99
Totale	247	aumentare	18	contagiato	84
		basso	17	contagiare	31
		crescita	13	ricovero	17
		aumento	9	ricoverato	13
		diminuire	9	ammalare	7
		abbassare	3	aggiornato	6
		discesa	2	Totale	697
		Totale	172		

5 Notes on the use of the affective dictionary

Due to the small size of the corpus and its specific context, some interventions were made on the *ELIta* affective dictionary (§5.1). These interventions are in addition to the evaluation of the dictionary’s coverage (§5.2) and (§5.3).

5.1 Domain lexicon and corrective interventions

In particular, an objection that could (rightly) be raised is that in this context a term like “positivo” (positive) could often have a negative valence, contrary to what happens in other contexts.

Table 5 presents the **ambivalent terms** — that is, those that could have *either* a positive *or* a negative valence — that we have identified¹²: some were completely removed from the analysis (*Not scored*), while others were removed only on some dimensions (*Neutralized*)¹³.

5.2 Lexicon coverage rate

To evaluate the dictionary coverage, the number of scored *tokens* and the percentage of coverage for each document (*lcr*, *lexicon coverage rate*) were calculated.

The overall coverage is 66.03%, including expansions (§5.3) and neutralizations (§5.1).

¹²The selection of terms to be neutralized was guided by a lexical correspondence analysis (LCA) and supplemented with criteria of synonymy and opposition, to ensure a balance of scores. We preferred to eliminate the terms, rather than assign them a neutral score (e.g., 5 on the 1-9 scale), to avoid introducing distortions in the calculation of the means.

¹³“Conte” was also not scored as in the corpus the name is always used as a proper noun (24 occurrences; the noun “conte” (count) is present in the dictionary). The name of Minister Speranza (the noun “speranza” means “hope”) was disambiguated.

Figure 13: Lexicon coverage rate in the headlines used in the LDA

5.3 Expansions

The check of lemmas not covered by *ELIta* led to the identification of a group of terms that could be “recovered” through *dictionary expansion* (or lexical enrichment), based on the assumption that words with the same root (or “lemma”) share a very similar emotional core (*Added* in Table 5).

In many cases, the expansion was “grammatical,” concerning substantivized or adjectivized participles, or reflexive forms of verbs¹⁴.

For other cases, *MultiWordNet* (Pianta et al., 2002) was used, a digital linguistic resource that organizes Italian words into sets of meanings called *synsets*—groups of terms that share the same meaning. These *synsets* are linked to affective scores in *SentiWordNet* (Baccianella et al., 2010; Esuli, 2019/2025) and are therefore particularly suitable for this purpose, unlike a common thesaurus¹⁵.

References

- Airoldi, E. M., Blei, D., Erosheva, E. A., & Fienberg, S. E. (Eds.). (2015). *Handbook of Mixed Membership Models and Their Applications* (1° edition). Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Albalawi, R., Yeap, T. H., & Benyoucef, M. (2020). Using topic modeling methods for short-text data: A comparative analysis. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 3. <https://doi.org/10/ghd4vd>
- Baccianella, S., Esuli, A., & Sebastiani, F. (2010). *Sentiwordnet 3.0: An enhanced lexical resource for sentiment analysis and opinion mining*. 10, 22002204. http://rec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2010/pdf/769_Paper.pdf
- Benoit, K., Watanabe, K., Wang, H., Nulty, P., Obeng, A., Müller, S., Matsuo, A., & Lowe, W. (2025). *Quanteda: Quantitative analysis of textual data*. <https://quanteda.io>
- Blei, D. M., Ng, A. Y., & Jordan, M. I. (2003). Latent dirichlet allocation. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 9931022.
- Blei, D., Ng, A., & Jordan, M. (2001). Latent dirichlet allocation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 14, 601608.

¹⁴Which are traced back to the verb root, inconsistently by different lemmatizers (and Italian language dictionaries).

¹⁵For example, *ELIta* contains “morte” (death) but not “decesso” (demise): since the latter is in the same synset as the former, the score of the former allowed for the “expansion” of coverage. The explicit link between the two resources (Italian and English with affective scores) is available in Vardanega (2025).

- Cazzola, C. (2020a). TOP 100 informazione online. A marzo crescite record per quasi tutti i quotidiani. In *Prima Comunicazione*. <https://www.primaonline.it/2020/05/14/306736/top-100-informazione-online-audiweb-a-marzo-crescite-record-per-quasi-tutti-i-quotidiani/>.
- Cazzola, C. (2020b). TOP 100 INFORMAZIONE ONLINE. A marzo l'emergenza mette il turbo alle audience. Ancora in testa Ciaopeople, editore di Fanpage e Cookist. In *Prima Comunicazione*. <https://www.primaonline.it/2020/05/04/306115/top-100-informazione-online-a-marzo-lemergenza-covid-fa-crescere-a-doppia-cifra-laudience-ancora-in-testa-ciaopeople-leditore-di-fanpage-e-cookist/>.
- Cazzola, C. (2020c). TOP 15 media italiani più attivi sui social. In marzo Sky Sport ancora primo, poi Il Corriere (che guadagna sei posizioni) e Fanpage. In *Prima Comunicazione*. <https://www.primaonline.it/2020/05/04/306080/top-15-dei-media-italiani-piu-attivi-sui-social-in-marzo-primo-e-ancora-sky-sport-secondo-il-corriere-della-sera-che-guadagna-sei-posizioni/>.
- Di Palma, E. (2024a). *ELIta (emotion lexicon for italian)*. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/OPEN-1036>
- Di Palma, E. (2024b). ELIta: A New Italian Language Resource for Emotion Analysis. *Proceedings of the 10th Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics (CLiC-it 2024)*, 297–307.
- Esuli, A. (2025). *Aesuli/SentiWordNet* [Computer software]. <https://github.com/aesuli/SentiWordNet> (Original work published 2019)
- Ferraris, M. (2017). *Postverità e altri enigmi*. Il Mulino.
- Friedman, D. (2022). *Topicdoc: Topic-specific diagnostics for LDA and CTM topic models*. <https://github.com/doug-friedman/topicdoc>
- Grün, B., & Hornik, K. (2024). *Topicmodels: Topic models*. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.topicmodels>
- Lorusso, A. M. (2018). *Postverità: Fra reality tv, social media e storytelling*. Editori Laterza.
- Nikita, M. (2020). *Ldatuning: Tuning of the latent dirichlet allocation models parameters*. <https://github.com/nikita-moor/ldatuning>
- Osgood, C., Saporta, S., & Nunnally, J. (1956). Evaluative assertion analysis. *Litera: Journal of Language, Literature and Culture Studies*, 3, 47–102.
- Phan, X.-H., Nguyen, L.-M., & Horiguchi, S. (2008). Learning to classify short and sparse text & web with hidden topics from large-scale data collections. *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on World Wide Web*, 91–100.
- Pianta, E., Bentivogli, L., & Girardi, C. (2002). *MultiWordNet: Developing an aligned multilingual database*. 293302. <https://cris.fbk.eu/handle/11582/499>
- Plutchik, R. (1980). A general psychoevolutionary theory of emotion. In R. Plutchik & H. Kellerman (Eds.), *Theories of Emotion* (pp. 3–33). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-558701-3.50007-7>
- R Core Team. (2025). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Russell, J. A. (1980). A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 39, 1161–1178.
- Russell, J. A., & Mehrabian, A. (1977). Evidence for a three-factor theory of emotions. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 11(3), 273–294.
- Shelton, T. (2020). A post-truth pandemic? *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 2053951720965612. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720965612>
- Van Dijck, J. (2014). Datafication, dataism and dataveillance: Big data between scientific paradigm and ideology. *Surveillance & Society*, 12(2), 197–208. <https://ojs.library.queensu.ca/index.php/surveillance-and-society/article/view/4776>
- Vardanega, A. (2025). *sentiwordnet_it 1.0*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17248244>